

Guidelines: How to prepare and transfer your data to the Archives

Fundamentals of records management

What is a record?

A **record** is any information, regardless of format, that is created, received, and maintained by an organization as evidence of a legal obligation or as a trace of administrative activity. This includes letters, reports, invoices, maps, photographs, contracts, and other documents that reflect the policies, decisions, and actions of the NGO and ensure their understanding in the future.

In contrast, some types of information are **not considered records**. These are referred to as non-record materials or items of temporary value. Examples include personal messages, reference documents, newsletters from external organizations, internal announcements with no evidentiary value, and blank forms. These types of content do not reflect decision-making or official actions.

Benefits and risks of good/poor records management

Benefits of good records management

- Enables quick access to and retrieval of information
- Supports business decision making
- Improves operational efficiency and effectiveness
- Enhances accountability and transparency
- Promotes good governance and development
- Identifies and protects vital information
- Ensures records are kept for as long as they are needed to support business needs and legal requirements.
- Supports preservation of institutional memory

Risks of poor records management

- Making poor decisions based on incomplete or out-of-date information
- Management cannot provide evidence of policies, decisions, actions and transactions
- Time is wasted trying to find records that are misfiled or lost
- Costs to the organization through lengthy searches and storage of obsolete records
- Information privacy and security is at risk if sensitive records are not managed appropriately
- In an emergency, vital records cannot be identified placing the organization's operations and its personnel at risk
- Inability to defend litigation properly which could in turn damage the organization's reputation
- Loss of valuable institutional memory

Why transfer records to the Archives?

Transferring records to the Archives ensures their long-term preservation in a secure, controlled environment. Beyond simply keeping documents, this process guarantees regulatory compliance, supports institutional memory, and enables operational continuity. RAS also adds significant value through structured metadata, traceability, and consistent archival standards.

Overview of the process

Before being safely preserved in the NGO Archives, your records will go through a structured process. This ensures that they are properly documented, stored, and remain accessible in the long term.

Here is how the process works:

1. **You prepare your data:** You select the documents that need to be transferred, organize them into folders and name files consistently.
2. **You complete the Archival Transfer of Custody (ATOC) form:** You fill in a simple form that describes what is being transferred and formally authorizes the transfer to the archives.
3. **You transfer your package to the Archives:** You send the ZIP package and ATOC form via the shared network drive provided by the Archives. Make sure to notify the Archives team once the transfer is complete.

Then, the Archives team will be able to process your records verifying their integrity and structure, enriching them with metadata, and organizing them for their long-term preservation.

The following sections will explain in detail how to do each step of the process.

1. How to prepare the data

Before transferring your documents to the Archives team, it's important to organize them.

The schema above shows the correct way to prepare your documents for transfer using a ZIP package.

Main folder (ZIP package)

At the top level, you must create one ZIP package clearly named with your name and a date range that reflects the time period covered by the records. This folder will serve as the container for everything you are transferring.

Folders

Within the main package, create one folder for each coherent group of documents related to a single specific matter or activity. For example, a meeting, a dispute case, a mission, a consultation, the preparation of a report, a negotiation, a training event, a legal case, the organization of a regional seminar, a trade policy review, etc.

Each folder should contain documents that naturally belong together. Avoid mixing unrelated materials.

Documents

Inside each folder, place all the documents relevant to that activity. Those documents can be reports, minutes, presentations, legal texts, correspondence, etc.

Avoid placing any document outside a folder. Every file must be inside a clearly named folder that reflects its content.

Do's and Don'ts

Do's	Don't's
Group documents by activity, case or purpose (e.g. one folder per meeting, project, or case).	Avoid grouping unrelated documents in the same folder.
Use clear, specific names that reflect the content (e.g. TradePolicyReview_Egypt_2023 or Panel_Report_DS476.pdf).	Do not use vague or generic names (e.g. Folder1, Misc, or Document1.docx, Scan0003.pdf).
Use unique and consistent naming for folders and files.	Avoid duplicate folder/file names (e.g., don't name every agenda just "Agenda.pdf").
Include final or approved versions of documents when possible.	Do not include duplicates or temporary files.
Keep all documents inside folders.	Avoid loose files at the root of the main ZIP package.

If uncertain, contact the Archives team for advice before transferring.

Examples of a good structure vs. a problematic one

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JohnSmith_2020
├── TradePolicyReview_Egypt_2023
│   ├── Opening_Statement.pdf
│   ├── Summary_Report.docx
│   └── Member_Comments.xlsx
├── LegalCase_EU_Article21
│   ├── Panel_Report.pdf
│   └── Correspondence_LegalUnit.docx

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JohnSmith_MessyFolder
├── Folder1
│   ├── Document1.docx
│   └── Scan0003.pdf
├── New Folder
│   └── Notes.txt
├── LooseFile1.pdf
└── Random.docx

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2. How to complete the Archival Transfer of Custody (ATOC) form

The Archival Transfer of Custody (ATOC) form serves as a formal instrument to document the transfer of responsibility for records from a division or staff member to the Archives.

A) Summary information

Begin by completing the first table of the form, which summarizes details about the package being transferred. This overview provides the Archives with the basic context of the transfer.

Field	Description	Example
Title of transfer	A short, descriptive title that reflects the content of the transfer.	Legal Affairs – Dispute Cases 2018–2022
Transfer authority Division, section, person, function	Name and/or position of the person authorizing the transfer. This person is responsible for the records.	John Smith, Director of Legal Affairs Division
Transfer quantity and unit of measure Number of electronic files and total size	Indicate the total number of digital elements being transferred. Right-click on the package and select “Properties”.	822 Mo, 103 files
Date range	Time span covered by the records. This refers to the dates the documents were created.	2018-2022
Language of records	List the languages present in the records.	English, French
Formats (paper, CD-ROMs, floppy disk, electronic files etc)	In our case, this will always be electronic files.	Electronic files
Remarks	Optional notes, clarifications, or instructions.	Includes scanned copies.
Date of transfer	Date the records are formally transferred to the Archives.	03.02.2025

B) Authorization

Next, fill in the Authorization section. This part must be signed by the person officially responsible for the transfer. By signing, the person confirms that:

- The records listed are being permanently transferred
- Archival processing by the Archives is authorized
- Standard access rules are accepted, including the 30-year rule for public access
- Any exceptions to access must be clearly marked in the inventory

This section also includes a counter-signature from the Archives team upon receipt.

C) Transfer inventory

Then, go to Annex 1: Transfer Inventory. For electronic records, only the second table is relevant (ignore the table on physical boxes and binders). In this table, list the contents of each folder to be transferred. Make sure the inventory accurately reflects the structure and content of the material being delivered.

Field	Description	Example
Folder name (by subject)	Name of the folder.	Trade Policy Review – Egypt 2023 Legal Case – Article 21 EU
File name	Exact name of the file as it appears in the folder, including extension if digital (e.g. .pdf, .docx).	Opening_Statement.pdf Correspondence_LegalUnit.docx
Date	Date of creation or use of the file. If a range applies, indicate the full span (e.g. YYYY or DD/MM/YYYY).	15.03.2022 2022–2023
Access restrictions	Indicate if the file contains confidential or restricted information.	Restricted Internal use only
Description	Brief summary of the content and purpose of the file.	Opening statement delivered by Egypt during the 2023 TPR session.
Remarks	Optional field for any clarification.	Draft version Scanned copy Password protected

3. How to transfer the data to the Archives

Package the data

Once your folders are correctly structured and named, compress the entire package into a single ZIP file. The ZIP file should include all the organized folders and the completed ATOC form. Name the ZIP file using the format: [YourName]_[DateRange].zip (e.g. Smith_2018-2022.zip).

Transfer method

Place the ZIP package and ATOC form in the shared network drive provided by the Archives team. Ensure that both files are fully copied and accessible.

Confirmation step

Notify the Archives team once the transfer is complete by sending a short confirmation email. The team will confirm receipt and begin processing the package.

Checklist

Structure your package

- The main folder (ZIP package) is clearly named: [YourName]_[DateRange]
- Each subfolder groups documents related to a single activity or case
- No unrelated documents are mixed across folders
- No loose files are left outside folders

Prepare your documents

- Duplicate or temporary files are removed
- File names are clear and consistent

Complete the ATOC form

- The first table (summary) is fully completed
- The Authorization section is signed
- The Transfer Inventory is completed (one row per folder)
- Any access restrictions are clearly indicated in the inventory

Package and transfer your data

- The entire folder structure is compressed into a single ZIP package
- The ATOC form is attached to the transfer
- Transfer is performed via shared network drive
- Archives team contact person is informed of the transfer

Final reminder

- A local copy of the transferred data is kept

Questions?

If you have any questions or need further guidance, please contact the Archives team at: [email]